

Chaos in Topological Spaces

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Abstract

We give a definition of chaos for a continuous self map f of a general topological space. This definition coincides with Devaney's definition for chaos when the topological space happens to be a metric space. This generalization is necessary to the study chaotic phenomena in relation to topological entropy.

We show that in a uniform Hausdorff space, there is a meaningful definition of sensitive dependence on initial conditions, and prove that if f is chaotic on a such a space, then f necessarily has sensitive dependence on initial conditions. The proof is interesting in that it explains very clearly what causes a chaotic process to have sensitive dependence.

Finally, we construct a chaotic map on a non-metrizable topological space.

INTRODUCTION

This note is put forward as a meaningful extension of the notion of chaos from metric to topological spaces. This generalization is worthwhile from different points of view. For example, it provides for the direct comparison and study of possible relations between chaos and topological entropy. Furthermore, as we show by construction, chaotic phenomena are present in non-metrizable spaces.

The point of departure here is the work of Banks et al.. [1]. This result states that, in a metric space, the first two components of Devaney's definition [2] — both purely topological — imply the third: sensitive dependence on initial conditions, which has a metric formulation. Because sensitive dependence is the only aspect of chaotic

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behavior that is open to experimental detection, it is considered by the scientific community to be the hallmark of chaotic behavior. Hence, anything one can say about sensitive dependence is important. We constructively explore the most general setting in which this phenomena occurs (a uniform Hausdorff space) and elucidate its cause.

SOME PRELIMINARIES

Since we will be concerned with uniform topological spaces, we recall briefly some definitions and facts concerning them. For more details we refer the reader to [3].

Let X be a nonvoid set and U, V nonvoid subsets of $X \times X$. Then U and V are relations on X . If $U \subset X \times X$, then $U^{-1} = \{(y, x) \mid (x, y) \in U\}$; $U \circ V = \{(x, z) \mid \text{for some } y, (x, y) \in V \text{ and } (y, z) \in U\}$; and the diagonal $\Delta(X) = \Delta = \{(x, x) \mid x \in X\}$.

Definition 1 A **uniformity** for a set X is a nonvoid collection \mathfrak{U} of subsets of $X \times X$ such that

- (1) each member of \mathfrak{U} contains Δ ;
- (2) if $U \in \mathfrak{U}$, then $U^{-1} \in \mathfrak{U}$;
- (3) if $U \in \mathfrak{U}$, then $V \circ V \subset U$ for some $V \in \mathfrak{U}$;
- (4) if U and V are members of \mathfrak{U} , then $U \cap V \in \mathfrak{U}$; and
- (5) if $U \in \mathfrak{U}$ and $U \subset V \subset X \times X$, then $V \in \mathfrak{U}$.

The pair (X, \mathfrak{U}) is called a **uniform space**.

A subcollection \mathcal{B} of a uniformity \mathfrak{U} is a **base** for \mathfrak{U} if and only if each element of \mathfrak{U} contains an element of \mathcal{B} .

For $x \in X$ and $U \in \mathfrak{U}$, define

$$U[x] = \{y \in X \mid (x, y) \in U\}.$$

Extend this to subsets A of X as follows:

$$U[A] = \bigcup_{x \in A} U[x] = \{y \in X \mid (x, y) \in U\}.$$

Definition 2 If (X, \mathfrak{U}) is a uniform space, the topology \mathcal{T} of the uniformity, called the **uniform topology**, is the collection of all subsets T of X such that for each $x \in T$ there is a $U \in \mathfrak{U}$ such that $U[x] \subset T$.

In fact, for each $x \in X$, the collection $\mathcal{U}_x = \{U[x] \mid U \in \mathfrak{U}\}$ forms a neighborhood base at x .

In this paper we employ the idea, due to A. Weil [4], of a uniform neighborhood system.

Definition 3 A **uniform neighborhood system** is a nonvoid set X , an arbitrary index set Λ , an ordering \succsim in Λ , and a function $V : \Lambda \times X \rightarrow \wp(X)$ such that the following conditions are satisfied:

- (1) for all $\alpha \in \Lambda$ and all $x \in X$, $V_\alpha(x)$ is a subset of X to which x belongs;
- (2) the relation \succsim directs the set Λ ;
- (3) if $\alpha \succsim \beta$, then $V_\alpha(x) \subset V_\beta(x)$ for all x .
- (4) for all $\alpha \in \Lambda$ there is a $\beta \in \Lambda$ such that $y \in V_\alpha(x)$ whenever $x \in V_\beta(y)$; and
- (5) for all $\alpha \in \Lambda$ there is a $\beta \in \Lambda$ such that $z \in V_\alpha(x)$ whenever $y \in V_\beta(x)$ and $z \in V_\beta(y)$.

If (V, \succsim) is a uniform neighborhood system for X , the collection of all sets $\{(x, y) \mid y \in V_\alpha(x)\}$ is base for a uniformity \mathfrak{U} of X , called the uniformity of the system. This uniformity has the property that for each $\alpha \in \Lambda$, there is some $U \in \mathfrak{U}$ such that $U[x] \subset V_\alpha(x)$ for all $x \in X$. Thus a uniform neighborhood system forms a neighborhood base at x , making X a topological space.

MAIN SECTION

For the remainder of the note, unless otherwise specified, X will represent an infinite uniform Hausdorff space. Also, we refer to the five axioms of a uniform neighborhood system found in definition 3 by UNS(*), where * is a positive integer between 1 and 5 inclusive.

Definition 4 If X is any nonvoid set and $f : X \rightarrow X$ any mapping of X , we define the set $O_f^+(x) = \{x, f(x), f^2(x), \dots\}$, where $f^n(x) = f[f^{n-1}(x)]$. $O_f^+(x)$ is called the **forward orbit** of x under f .

Notation: For simplicity, if the mapping f is understood and there is no danger of confusion, we will write $O(x)$ in place of $O_f^+(x)$. Also, we will sometimes write $f^k(x) = x_k$, so that $O(x) = \{x, x_1, x_2, \dots\}$.

Definition 5 If X is any topological space and $f : X \rightarrow X$ any continuous mapping of X , then f is said to be **transitive** on X if for any two nonvoid open subsets U and V of X , there is a positive integer n such that $f^n(U) \cap V \neq \emptyset$.

Definition 6 Let X be any nonvoid set and $f : X \rightarrow X$ any mapping. If for some positive integer n , $f^n(x) = x$ but $f^k(x) \neq x$ for all k , $1 \leq k \leq n - 1$, then x is called a **periodic point of f** with primitive period n .

Notation: We denote the set of all periodic points in X by $Per(X)$.

Definition 7 Let X be a topological space and $f : X \rightarrow X$ a continuous map. f is said to be **chaotic** on X provided that any two nonvoid open subsets of X share a periodic orbit – that is, given U and V nonvoid and open in X , there is a periodic point p in X such that

$$U \cap O(p) \neq \emptyset \quad \text{and} \quad V \cap O(p) \neq \emptyset.$$

Proposition Let X be a topological space and $f : X \rightarrow X$ be continuous. f is chaotic on X if and only if f is transitive and the periodic points of f are dense in X .

Proof If f is chaotic on X , then every pair of open sets share a periodic orbit; in particular, the periodic points are dense in X . Given $U, V \subset X$ non-void open sets, there is a periodic point p and $x, y \in O(p)$ with $x \in U$ and $y \in V$ and some positive integer k such that $f^k(x) = y$, so that $f^k(U) \cap V \neq \emptyset$.

On the other hand, the transitivity of f on X implies that given $U, V \subset X$ open and non-void, there is a k such that for some $x \in U$, $f^k(x) \in V$. Now define $W = f^{-k}(V) \cap U$. Then W is open and non-void with the property that $f^k(W) \subset V$. But since the periodic points of f are dense in X , there is a $p \in W$ such that $f^k(p) \in V$. This shows that U, V share the orbit of p – that is, $U \cap O(p) \neq \emptyset$ and $V \cap O(p) \neq \emptyset$.

Remark. Easy examples show that topological transitivity and the density of the periodic points are independent; for example, a rotation of a cylinder by $\pi/4$ radians has dense periodic points but no transitivity, while an irrational rotation of the circle has transitivity but no periodic points.

Definition 8 Let $f : X \rightarrow X$ be continuous. f is said to have **sensitive dependence on initial conditions** provided there exists $\alpha \in \Lambda$ such that for all $x \in X$ and every neighborhood $N(x)$ of x , there exists $y \in N(x)$ ($y \neq x$), and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $f^n(x) \notin V_\alpha(f^n(y))$. α is called the **sensitivity index** of f .

Lemma 1 There exists $\eta \in \Lambda$ such that for all $x \in X$ there is a $q \in Per(X)$ with

$$V_\eta(q_k) \cap \{x\} = \emptyset \quad \text{for all} \quad q_k \in O(q).$$

Proof. Let r, s be distinct periodic points, so that $O(r) \cap O(s) = \emptyset$. First, observe that there exists $\eta \in \Lambda$ such that for all $r_k \in O(r)$ and $s_k \in O(s)$,

$$V_\eta(r_k) \cap V_\eta(s_k) = \emptyset.$$

For $O(r)$ and $O(s)$ are finite and disjoint, so that their union is finite and for every pair x, y in the union, there is a $\beta \in \Lambda$ such that $V_\beta(x) \cap V_\beta(y) = \emptyset$, since X is a uniform Hausdorff space. Take the supremum over all such indices and call it η .

Now let $x \in X$. Since r, s are distinct periodic points, if $x \notin V_\eta(r_k)$ for all $r_k \in O(r)$, letting $r = q$ gives the result. If $x \in V_\eta(r_k)$ for some $r_k \in O(r)$, then $x \notin V_\eta(s_k)$ for all $s_k \in O(s)$ and again, letting $s = q$, we are done.

Lemma 2 There exists $\alpha \in \Lambda$ such that for all $x \in X$ there is a periodic point $q \in X$ with

$$V_\alpha(q_k) \cap V_\alpha(x) = \emptyset \quad \text{for all } q_k \in O(q).$$

Proof. Select any $x \in X$ and let η and q be as in Lemma 1, so that for each $q_k \in O(q)$, $x \notin V_\eta(q_k)$. Using UNS(5), given this η , there is a $\beta \in \Lambda$ such that

$$x \in V_\eta(q_k) \quad \text{whenever } y \in V_\beta(q_k) \quad \text{and } x \in V_\beta(y).$$

Thus for all $y \in V_\beta(q_k)$, $x \notin V_\beta(y)$, since otherwise, we would have that $x \in V_\eta(q_k)$, contradicting what we are assuming to be true.

Now by UNS(4), given β , there exists β_0 such that if $y \in V_{\beta_0}(x)$, then $x \in V_\beta(y)$. But we have just shown that for all $y \in V_\beta(q_k)$, $x \notin V_\beta(y)$. Therefore, for all $y \in V_\beta(q_k)$, $y \notin V_{\beta_0}(x)$. Hence $V_\beta(q_k) \cap V_{\beta_0}(x) = \emptyset$; and since \succ directs Λ , we may choose $\alpha \in \Lambda$ such that $\alpha \succ \beta$ and $\alpha \succ \beta_0$. Thus α is independent of x (since η is independent of x and β depends only on η , while β_0 depends only on β) and we see (by UNS(3)) that

$$V_\alpha(x) \cap V_\alpha(q_k) = \emptyset \quad \text{for all } q_k \in O(q)$$

which completes the proof.

Theorem 1. Let X be a uniform Hausdorff space and $f : X \rightarrow X$ a continuous mapping. If f is chaotic, then f has sensitive dependence on initial conditions.

Proof. Given x, α, q as in lemma 2.

Denoting $q_i = f^i(q)$,

let $W_0 = V_\alpha(q_n)$, and for $1 \leq i \leq n$,

$W_i = f^{-1}(W_{i-1}) \cap V_\alpha(q_{n-i})$.

Then $f^i(W_n) \subset W_{n-i} \subset V_\alpha(q_i)$. Choose any open neighborhood N_x of x , calling

$U = N_x \cap V_\alpha(x)$.

Since the periodic points are dense in X , there exists a $p \in U$ with primitive period n .

By transitivity, there exists $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $f^k(U) \cap W_n \neq \emptyset$,
which means there exists $y \in U$ such that $f^k(y) \in W_n$.

Write $k = an - b$ for $0 \leq b \leq n - 1$.

Then $f^{an}(y) = f^b(f^k(y)) \in f^b(W_n) \subset W_{n-b} \subset V_\beta(q_b)$,

and since the primitive period of p is n , $f^{an}(p) \in U$.

By lemma 2 $V_\alpha(q_b) \cap V_\alpha(x) = \emptyset$, which implies that $f^{an}(y), f^{an}(p)$ are α -separated.

The question is, where is $f^{an}(x)$?

If $f^{an}(x) \in V_\alpha(q_b)$ then $f^{an}(x), f^{an}(p)$ are α -separated, since $V_\alpha(q_b) \cap V_\alpha(p) = \emptyset$.

If $f^{an}(x) \notin V_\alpha(q_b)$, then $f^{an}(x) \notin V_\alpha(f^{an}(y))$,

Because, $f^{an}(y) \in V_\alpha(q_b) \subset V_\alpha(q_b)$.

Hence, $f^{an}(x) \notin V_\alpha(f^{an}(y))$, so that $f^{an}(x), f^{an}(y)$ are α -separated.

Likewise, if $f^{an}(x) \in V_\alpha(x)$ then $f^{an}(x), f^{an}(y)$ are α -separated.

In a similar way, one shows that

If $f^{an}(x) \notin V_\alpha(x)$, then $f^{an}(x) \notin V_\alpha(f^{an}(p))$,

Because, $V_\alpha(x) \supset V_\alpha(x) \supset U$, and $p \in U$.

Hence, $f^{an}(x) \notin V_\alpha(x) \Rightarrow f^{an}(x) \notin V_\alpha(p)$, so that $f^{an}(x), f^{an}(p)$ are α -separated.

In any case, $f^{an}(x)$ is α -separated from one of $f^{an}(y), f^{an}(p)$,

showing that f has sensitive dependence on initial conditions, with index of sensitivity α .

A CHAOTIC MAP ON A NON-METRIZABLE TOPOLOGICAL SPACE

The cantor set, as a topological space, can be realized as the set of all sequences of zeros and ones with appropriate basic neighborhoods. That is, $C = \{f : \mathcal{N} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}\}$.

We mimic this construction with \mathcal{N} replaced by an uncountable set A and an adjustment of basic neighborhoods.

The Cantor Space C over A :

Let A be a infinite set. Let $C = \{0, 1\}^A$ be the set of functions from A to $\{0, 1\}$.

For each finite set $B \subset A$ and each map $\phi \in \{0, 1\}^B$, let $N(B, \phi) = \{f \in C | f(x) = \phi(x) \text{ for } x \in B\}$.

Let \mathcal{T}_C be the topology whose basis is the set $\{N(B, \phi) | B \subset A \text{ finite and } \phi \in \{0, 1\}^B\}$.

(C, \mathcal{T}_C) is the Cantor Space which, not having a countable neighborhood base, is a non-metrizable topological space.

Lemma 3

Let $A = \cup_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} A_\alpha$ where $A_\alpha = \{x_{\alpha,i} | i \in \mathcal{N}\}$ is countable and $\alpha \neq \beta \implies A_\alpha \cap A_\beta = \emptyset$. For each finite set $S \subset \mathcal{A}$, $k \in \mathcal{N}$, define $K(S, k) = \{x_{\alpha,i} | \alpha \in S, 1 \leq i \leq k\}$. Then $\{N(K(S, k), \psi) | \psi \in \{0, 1\}^K\}$ is a basis for \mathcal{T}_C .

Proof This is an easy check.

Theorem 2 If $\sigma : C \longrightarrow C$ is defined by $(\sigma f)(x_{\alpha,i}) = f(x_{\alpha,(i+1)})$ then σ is chaotic.

Proof σ is topologically transitive:

Let $U, V \subset \mathcal{T}_C$. By lemma 3, there exist sets $K(S_1, k_1), K(S_2, k_2)$ and ϕ_1, ϕ_2 such that $N(K(S_1, k_1), \phi_1) \subset U$ and $N(K(S_2, k_2), \phi_2) \subset V$. Let $S = S_1 \cup S_2$, $K = K(S, k_1 + k_2)$ and $\psi : K \longrightarrow \{0, 1\}$. Define ψ on $K(S, k_1 + k_2)$ by

$$\psi(x_{\alpha,i}) = \begin{cases} \phi_1(x_{\alpha,i}) & \text{if } \alpha \in S_1 \text{ and } i \leq k_1 \\ \phi_2(x_{\alpha,i-k_1}) & \text{if } \alpha \in S_2 \text{ and } i > k_1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Since $\psi(x) = \phi_1(x)$ for $x \in K(S_1, k_1)$ it follows that $N(K(S, k_1 + k_2), \psi) \subset N(K(S_1, k_1), \phi_1)$. If $f \in N(K(S, k_1 + k_2), \psi)$ then $(\sigma^{k_1} f)(x) = \phi_2(x)$ for $x \in K(S_2, k_1)$ and it follows that $\sigma^{k_1} N(K(S, k_1 + k_2), \psi) \subset N(K(S_2, k_2), \phi_2)$. That is, $\sigma^{k_1}(U) \cap V \neq \emptyset$. The set of

periodic points of σ are dense in C :

Let $U \in \mathcal{T}_C$. By lemma 3, there exists $N(K(S, k), \phi) \subset U$.

Define $f \in N(K(S, k), \phi)$ by

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \phi(x_{\alpha,i}) & \text{if } x \in \{x_{\alpha,j} | \alpha \in S, 1 \leq i \leq k, \text{ and } j = k\lambda + i, \lambda = 0, 1, 2, \dots\} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Then $\sigma^k f = f$.

Note C admits a uniformity but is not metrizable.

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